

Integrating Information Technology, Knowledge Management, And Human Resource Management to Enhance Employee Performance: The Role of Organizational Culture

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ABSTRACT

A The aim of this study is to validate the measurement instruments for Information Technology (IT), Knowledge Management (KM), Human Resource Management (HRM), and organizational culture dimensions and to assess their influence on employee performance in the context of Aviation sector industry. Despite the recognized importance of these internal organizational capabilities, there is a lack of studies that integrate IT, KM, HRM, and organizational culture simultaneously to examine their collective effect on employee performance. This study employed a quantitative research approach using a pilot survey design. A total of 42 senior employees and managers from Global Aerospace Logistics in Abu Dhabi, UAE participated in the survey. Data were analyzed using SPSS, assessing reliability and internal consistency with Cronbach's Alpha and corrected item-total correlations. Key findings revealed significant positive correlations between IT and KM capabilities and employee performance, while HRM components showed positive but mostly non-significant relationships. Among organizational culture dimensions, market and hierarchy cultures were strongly associated with employee performance. These results provide a solid foundation for further analysis using PLS-SEM to test the proposed research hypotheses and offer practical insights for improving employee performance through the effective integration of organizational capabilities.

KEYWORDS: Information Technology, Knowledge, Human Resource, Employee Performance.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is an extremely important concept that relates to an organization's outcome and success (Cahyadi et al., 2022). It is measured by key constructs such as overall input and productivity on the job (Jiang et al., 2023). Hence, the performance of an employee is an important key to performance effectiveness. The best performance of times is often the basic result that an organization wants to achieve (Abudaqa et al., 2020). Also, performance is the extent to which an individual carries out an assignment or task (Cabaluna, 2022). In other words, it refers to the degree of accomplishment of the task that makes up an employee's job requirements (Tampol, 2021). According to Setiawan et al (2021), individual performance is generally determined by three factors, the desire to do the

job as well as the capacity to do the job, and the work environment and information required to do the job. However, there are numerous other organizational internal factors that significantly impacting employees performance; the organizational human resources, information technology, knowledge management and innovation capabilities as well as culture and values of the organization play a vital role in improving overall employee performance (Setiawan et al., 2021; Alshehhi et al., 2021).

Information technology (IT) devices that are connected to the internet, such as computers, tablets, and smartphones, are ubiquitous at work. These IT devices have greatly facilitated employees' job task performance (Labetubun et al., 2022). In today's critical work environment, organizations must be more intelligent and adapt to radical changes, offsetting

threats and exploiting market opportunities (Bel *et al.*, 2020). The rapidly changing business environment pressures companies to put in more effort to survive (Turulja and Bajgorić, 2015; Al-Marri *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, enabling IT in organizational activities addresses the sense of what is happening in the external environment, and it defines how to process the incoming data to improve the overall performance (Chu *et al.*, 2019).

Knowledge Management (KM) refers to the systematic process of acquiring, creating, sharing, and utilizing knowledge to achieve strategic and operational goals (Alegre, 2012; Suryani *et al.*, 2020). It improves efficiency, fosters innovation, and builds sustainable competitive advantage, while also enhancing employee performance by developing skills, encouraging collaboration, and supporting informed decision-making (Kumta, 2018; Robith *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, Human Resource Management (HRM) encompasses policies and practices such as recruitment, training, compensation, and performance appraisal that shape employee behavior, attitudes, and performance (Lee, 2018; Reza, 2019). By strengthening employees' ability, motivation, and opportunity to perform, HRM fosters commitment and effective workplace behaviors, serving as the backbone of organizational success (Thin *et al.*, 2021; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). Thus, KM and HRM play a complementary role in driving employee performance and achieving organizational competitiveness (Pradana *et al.*, 2022).

Organizational culture is the shared system of values, norms, and assumptions that shape how people behave and how work is carried out (Armstrong, 2006; Schein 2004). It operates both visibly through rules and practices and subconsciously through deeper beliefs, influencing organizational identity and performance (Mohelska and Sokolova, 2018). Hence, organizational culture is also a crucial determinant of employee performance. Prior research highlights that the culture adopted within organizations significantly shapes overall outcomes (Hofstede, 2011; Haider *et al.*, 2015; Jardiou *et al.*, 2020; Agarwal and Gupta, 2021; Kakarougkas, 2023). Cultural characteristics influence strategic decisions, such as the adoption of information technology, and differences in cultural values can determine the extent to which technology generates benefits (Afum *et al.*, 2020). Diverse cultures embody distinct values, assumptions, and expectations that directly or indirectly affect organizational practices (Dhanhani and Abdullah, 2019). For example, in the UAE, despite rapid IT adoption, issues such as privacy and trust remain culturally sensitive (AlShehhi *et al.*, 2021). Thus, organizational culture not only shapes technology integration but also emerges as a dominant factor influencing the benefits derived from information and communication technologies (Subramanian and Suresh, 2023; Junianti and Rony, 2023). Ultimately, a supportive culture, combined with effective

HRM practices, strengthens employee performance and maximizes organizational competitiveness.

The aim of this paper is to introduce a conceptual model that integrates IT, KM, and HRM to enhance Employee Performance, with organizational culture serving as a mediating factor. The novelty of this study lies in its holistic approach, as it simultaneously examines the interplay of IT, KM, HRM, and organizational culture often studied in isolation thereby offering a more comprehensive understanding of their combined impact on employee performance.

2.0 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Information Technology (IT)

Information Technology (IT) broadly refers to programs, computers, and telecommunications, while IT competency encompasses the effective use of these technologies to satisfy a company's information needs (Kamariotou, 2018). IT has become integral to organizational functions, supporting information management and overall performance (Lutfi *et al.*, 2017; Aydiner *et al.*, 2019). IT capability is defined as a firm's ability to acquire, deploy, combine, and reconfigure IT resources to support business processes and strategies (Salunke *et al.*, 2019). Literature identifies IT capability as a multidimensional construct that includes IT infrastructure flexibility, IT human capital, and IT partnership quality, all of which are critical for organizational learning (Bakan *et al.*, 2017). By enabling the acquisition, sharing, and application of knowledge with greater speed and accuracy, IT capability strengthens learning processes, enhances efficiency, and optimizes organizational performance (Bakan *et al.*, 2017; Galliers *et al.*, 2020; Darwis *et al.*, 2023).

Organizations increasingly adopt IT applications as competitive tools to enhance efficiency and employee performance (Nuskiya, 2018); Trieu *et al.*, 2023). Empirical studies demonstrate that IT capability contributes to managing data, improving productivity, and supporting organizational activities (Foresti *et al.*, 2015; Sukmawan, 2020; Szabó, 2021; Darwis *et al.*, 2023). Research further highlights its positive impact on employee empowerment, innovativeness, and firm performance Roman *et al.* (2018), as well as on human resource productivity (Yuvaraj, 2018). Similarly, Sukmawan (2020) found that effective information systems significantly improve employee performance, underscoring the role of IT as a driver of organizational success.

2.2 Knowledge Management (KM)

Knowledge Management (KM) is broadly defined as the process of identifying, creating, sharing, and applying knowledge to improve organizational effectiveness (Boshara *et al.*, 2015; Ahmad Saleh *et al.*, 2018; Suryani *et al.*, 2020). It transforms individual knowledge into organizational assets

through dynamic interactions that enhance efficiency and innovation (Oktari et al., 2020). Building on this, Knowledge Management Capability (KMC) refers to an organization’s ability to continually and deliberately generate, integrate, and apply knowledge to sustain competitiveness (Chiu and Chen, 2016). Furthermore, Gold et al (2001) identified infrastructural and process capabilities as direct determinants of organizational effectiveness, while subsequent research emphasizes that KMC enhances employee productivity, product quality, customer service, innovation, and flexibility (Tseng, 2016; Robith et al., 2021). Ultimately, firms with strong KMC are better positioned to leverage diverse knowledge sources, create value, and gain sustainable competitive advantage (Chiu and Chen, 2016; Salzano et al., 2016).

KM is a continuous process that enables employees to consult, share, and apply knowledge to enhance their work (Soto-Acosta et al., 2018). Prior research has consistently demonstrated a positive relationship between KM capability and organizational performance (Abualoush et al., 2018; Mardani et al., 2018; Zaim et al., 2019; Singgih et al., 2020; Ghani et al., 2020; Migdadi, 2021; Shahzad et al., 2020; Phuong, 2022). For example, Zhuo (2017) found that the ability to apply knowledge significantly enhances the technical performance of human resource management systems, while Hosseini et al (2014) highlighted the impact of explicit and tacit knowledge on supply chain performance. Other studies confirm that KM practices such as knowledge creation, sharing, storage, and application positively affect employee performance (Jayashri and Kalaiselvi, 2018; Biswakarma, 2018; Al Ahbab et al., 2019). Overall, KM enables organizations to achieve sustainable competitive advantage while improving employee creativity, productivity, and organizational effectiveness (Mansour, 2020).

2.3 Human Resource Management (HRM)

Human Resource Management (HRM) encompasses the policies, practices, and systems that manage employees and influence their behavior, attitudes, and performance (Snell et al., 2015). It includes activities such as human resource planning, job analysis, recruitment, selection, orientation, compensation, training and development, performance appraisal, and labor relations (Shaukat et al. (2015). HRM involves all management decisions that affect the relationship between the organization and its employees, ensuring that human resources are effectively utilized to achieve organizational goals Tabouli et al (2016). Effective HRM practices have been shown to improve employee performance and, in turn, enhance overall organizational performance (Kenedi et al., 2022).

HRM practices play a critical role in enhancing employee performance, which in turn helps organizations achieve their goals (Nataraja and Alamri, 2016). HRM practices are considered internally coherent and consistent mechanisms designed to strengthen employee competence and motivation (Abuhjeeleh et al., 2019). Empirical studies have confirmed the positive impact of HRM capabilities on employee performance. For instance, Ngwenya and Aigbavboa (2017) found a significant relationship between HRM practices employee performance. Similarly, Khoreva and Wechtler (2018) reported that HR dimensions skill, motivation, and opportunity enhancement positively influenced innovative job performance among professional service employees in Finland. Mira et al (2019) also observed a significant positive relationship between HR practices (training, development, rewards, job analysis, recruitment, employee relations, and empowerment) and employee performance among Saudi port authority employees. Likewise, Rodjam et al (2020) confirmed that HR practices such as training, performance appraisal, rewards, and employee empowerment significantly improve employee performance.

2.4 Organizational culture

Organizational culture encompasses the collective behaviors, attitudes, values, and assumptions of its members (F. Shahzad, 2014). It is a key determinant of an organization’s competitive performance, strategic direction, and uniqueness (Zamir, 2018). Organizational culture can be described as a complex set of ideas, values, and symbols that shape how organizations carry out their activities and achieve efficiency and productivity (Etalong, 2022). It also includes the norms experienced by members in their work settings, which guide behavior and adaptation to achieve organizational goals (Schneider et al., 2013; Khan et al., 2020). Moreover, organizational culture influences how members interact with each other and with external stakeholders (Lau et al., 2020).

The relationship between organizational culture and employee performance has been examined in various contexts (Wambugu, 2014; Körner et al., 2015; Rashid, 2020; Mara et al., 2020; Ekaningsih et al 2020; Lau et al., 2020; Mohsen and Neyazi, 2020; Ahmad et al., 2021). Studies consistently report a positive and significant impact of organizational culture on performance. For example, Ali et al., (2019) found that organizational culture positively influenced safety performance in the UAE’s oil and gas industry, supported by Al-hammadi and Asma (2020). Similarly, Al Dhanhani and Abdullah (2021) showed that organizational culture, alongside transformational leadership, significantly affects employees’ job performance. Noora et al (2021) and Cherian et al (2021) also reported that organizational culture enhances employee attitudes, behavior, and overall performance, confirming its critical role in improving workplace outcomes.

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Furthermore, several studies have highlighted its critical role as a mediator between organizational practices and performance outcomes (Shami, 2021; Amin et al., 2022; Marlapa et al., 2024). For example, Khalifa (2021) found that organizational culture mediates the relationship between innovation capacity and organizational performance in the UAE, while Alhmoudi et al (2021) showed that organizational culture mediates the link between strategic planning and organizational excellence. Similarly, Hong et al. (2022) demonstrated that organizational culture mediates the impact of organizational citizenship behavior and innovative work behavior on employee performance in the education sector in Malaysia. Although some studies, such as Rasool and Soomro (2021) and Sabuhari et al. (2021) reported non-significant mediation effects in certain contexts, these mixed findings underscore that organizational culture influence can vary depending on the organizational factor and environment. Overall, the literature indicates that organizational culture acts as a bridge, turning organizational resources like TI, KM, and HRM capabilities into enhanced employee performance Aman et al., 2018; Tariq Al zoubi and Rumman, 2020; Alshammari, 2020; Saleem and Ilkhanizadeh, 2021; Setyawan et al., 2021; Amin et al., 2022). However, there remains a noticeable gap in research exploring organizational culture as a mediator between IT, KM, and HRM capabilities and employee performance.

3.0 THE CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Integrating IT, KM, and HRM is essential for enhancing employee performance as each element reinforces the others in promoting efficiency and effectiveness. IT capability enables organizations to manage and analyze data, improving

productivity and employee performance (Trieu et al., 2023; Nuskiya, 2018; Roman et al., 2018). KM ensures that knowledge is created, shared, and applied effectively, positively influencing employee creativity, innovation, and overall job performance (Soto-Acosta et al., 2018; Biswakarma, 2018; Mansour, 2020). HRM practices, including training, development, rewards, and empowerment, strengthen employee motivation and competence, directly impacting job performance (Nataraja & Alamri, 2016; Mira et al., 2019; Rodjam et al., 2020). Therefore, organizational culture acts as a critical mediator in this model as it shapes how employees interact with these systems, adopts new practices, and translates available resources into performance outcomes. A strong, supportive culture encourages knowledge sharing, effective use of IT tools, and engagement with HRM practices, thereby amplifying their combined effect on employee performance (Ali et al., 2019; Al Dhanhani & Abdullah, 2021; Cherian et al., 2021).

In the proposed model, IT, KM, and HRM are positioned as independent variables that drive employee performance the dependent variable. However, their effects are not always direct; they are shaped by the organizational culture, which functions as a mediating variable. organizational culture provides an environment that determines how effectively IT tools are used, how knowledge is shared, and how HRM practices are implemented. A positive culture encourages collaboration, innovation, and adaptability, thereby amplifying the effect of IT, KM, and HRM on employee performance (Ali et al., 2019; Al Dhanhani and Abdullah, 2021; Cherian et al., 2021). The conceptual model illustrates in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: A Conceptual Model of Integrating IT, KM, and HRM with Organization Culture as mediator on Employee Performance

Based on insights from earlier studies, this research develops a series of hypotheses for testing. Prior work has shown that IT, KM, and HRM capabilities play an important role in improving employee performance, whether directly or when supported by the organizational environment (Ali et al., 2019; Al Dhanhani and Abdullah, 2021; Cherian et al., 2021). At the same time, organizational culture has been consistently recognized not only as a direct driver of performance but also as a mediator that enhances the impact of these capabilities (Rasool and Soomro, 2021; Khalifa, 2021; Alhmoudi et al., 2021). Building on this evidence, the present study proposes the following hypotheses.

- H1: Information Technology (IT) capability positively influences employee performance.*
- H2: Knowledge Management (KM) capability positively influences employee performance.*
- H3: Human Resource Management (HRM) capability positively influences employee performance.*
- H4: Organizational culture positively influences employee performance.*
- H5: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between Information Technology (IT) capability and employee performance.*
- H6: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between Knowledge Management (KM) capability and employee performance.*
- H7: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between Human Resource Management (HRM) capability and employee performance.*

4.0 KEY CONSTRUCTS OF THE STUDY

4.1 The elements of IT Capability

IT capability refers to an organization’s ability to mobilize and deploy IT-based resources in combination with other resources and capabilities (Podsakoff et al., 2016). For this study, IT capability is measured through three key dimensions:

1. IT Knowledge: The skills and expertise employees possess to effectively use IT resources. Strong IT knowledge enables employees to adapt to technological changes, improve problem-solving, and increase work efficiency (Nuskiya, 2018)
2. IT Operations: The ability to manage IT systems, applications, and processes for daily operations. Effective IT operations ensure smooth workflow, reduce errors, and enhance productivity, which contributes to overall employee performance (Hao et al., 2025)
3. IT Infrastructure: The physical and digital foundations (hardware, software, networks, databases) that support organizational processes (Trieu et al., 2023). A robust IT infrastructure provides reliable access to knowledge and tools, enabling collaboration and performance improvement (Hao et al., 2025).

4.2 The elements of KM Capability

KM capability refers to an organization’s ability to systematically acquire, convert, and apply knowledge to enhance decision-making, innovation, and performance (Gold et al., 2001; Chiu and Chen, 2016). For this study, KM capability is conceptualized through three core dimensions:

1. KM Acquisition: The ability to identify, capture, and acquire valuable knowledge from internal and external sources. This ensures employees have access to relevant insights that strengthen problem-solving and innovation (Zhuo, 2017; Biswakarma, 2018).
2. KM Conversion: The process of organizing, integrating, and sharing knowledge across the organization. Effective conversion transforms tacit and explicit knowledge into actionable insights, fostering collaboration and efficiency (Schoenherr et al., 2014; Rosmaini & Toh, 2020).
3. KM Application: The ability to apply acquired and converted knowledge to practical tasks and decisions. This directly enhances employee performance through improved creativity, innovation, and operational outcomes (Mansour, 2020; Hong et al., 2022)

4.3 The elements of HRM Capability

HRM capability refers to the organization’s ability to design and implement practices that enhance employee motivation, skills, and commitment, ultimately leading to improved performance (Deepalakshmi et al., 2024). For this study, HRM capability is represented through three key dimensions:

1. Compensation and Rewards Fair and competitive compensation systems, along with recognition and rewards, enhance employee motivation and commitment. Such practices have been shown to strengthen job satisfaction and performance (Mira et al., 2019; Rodjam et al., 2020).
2. Job Security Providing employees with a sense of stability fosters trust, loyalty, and psychological safety. This reduces turnover intention and motivates employees to fully engage in their work (Khoreva and Wechtler, 2018).
3. Training and Development Continuous skill-building opportunities equip employees with the competencies required to perform effectively and innovate. Training initiatives are strongly linked to long-term organizational success (Nadarajah et al., 2012; Mira et al., 2019).

4.4 The elements of Organizational Culture

Organizational culture provides the shared values, norms, and assumptions that shape how employees interact and perform within the workplace (Etalong, 2022; Khan et al., 2020). To capture the multidimensional nature of culture, this study adopts the Competing Values Framework (CVF), which classifies organizational culture into four dimensions:

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1. **Team Culture (Clan Culture):** Emphasizes collaboration, trust, and employee involvement. Such cultures enhance loyalty, communication, and job satisfaction, which in turn improve employee performance (Cherian et al., 2021).
2. **Adhocracy Culture:** Focuses on innovation, adaptability, and risk-taking. Organizations with adhocracy cultures encourage creativity and empower employees to experiment, leading to higher levels of innovative job performance (Hong et al., 2022).
3. **Market Culture:** Oriented toward competitiveness, productivity, and goal achievement. This culture motivates employees through performance-driven rewards and external positioning, fostering accountability and measurable performance outcomes (Al Dhanhani and Abdullah, 2021).
4. **Hierarchy Culture:** Characterized by structure, stability, and control. By providing clear rules, procedures, and authority lines, hierarchy cultures ensure efficiency, consistency, and reliable job performance outcomes (Rasool & Soomro, 2021).

In the conceptual model, organizational culture is not only a critical factor influencing employee behavior but also serves as a mediator that channels the effects of IT capability, KM capability, and HRM capability into improved employee performance. For instance, training and IT infrastructure may only be effective when the culture encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing (Ali et al., 2019; Cherian et al., 2021). Similarly, reward systems or knowledge application efforts are best translated into results when aligned with supportive cultural values that promote adaptability and innovation (Al Dhanhani & Abdullah, 2021; Hong et al., 2022). Prior studies have highlighted that without a conducive culture, the potential of IT, KM, and HRM practices remains underutilized, whereas a strong organizational culture significantly amplifies their impact on employee performance (Noora et al., 2021; Alhmoudi et al., 2021).

5.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A quantitative research method was adopted to achieve the study's objectives, with a survey questionnaire used as the data collection tool. Research design is critical for guiding the collection and analysis of data, ensuring that research questions are effectively addressed (Creswell, 2012). It represents the overall strategy selected to logically investigate the study components and provide answers to the research problem (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). A carefully chosen design not only ensures methodological accuracy but also strengthens the reliability of the study's findings (Pearse, 2019).

5.1 Survey Instrumentation

The questionnaire's instrumentation was adapted from previously published studies. IT capability was measured

based on its three elements that are IT knowledge, IT operations, and IT infrastructure using 15 items adopted from Turulja and Bajgoric (2017) and Shami (2021). KM capability, based on its three elements that are knowledge acquisition, conversion, and application were measured with 21 items from Alegre (2012) and Shami (2021). HRM capability was assessed through 19 items covering compensation and rewards, job security, and training and development, identified as critical factors influencing employee performance (Alnaqbi, 2011). All items achieved reliability within the accepted range (Koç et al., 2014; Al Adresi and Darun, 2017; Jawaad et al., 2019; Khuong et al., 2020). Organizational culture was measured across four dimensions adhocracy, hierarchy, market, and clan culture, using 20 items adopted from Cameron and Quinn (2011), Tabouli et al. (2016), Nam (2022), and Elnagar et al. (2022). Finally, employee job performance was measured with 10 items adopted from Pradhan (2018), Yuvaraj (2018), and Pazetto et al. (2022).

5.2 Sampling Method

A stratified random sampling technique was employed in this study. This method is suitable when the population is heterogeneous but can be divided into relatively homogeneous subgroups, or strata (Pirzadeh et al., 2011). The population was divided into three strata: Global Aerospace Logistics, EDGE Group Abu Dhabi, and Etihad Engineering. Proportional samples were then drawn from each stratum to ensure balanced representation. This proportional allocation strengthens both the accuracy and the generalizability of the study's findings (Pirzadeh et al., 2011; Taherdoost, 2017). The aim of this paper is to confirm the components of the IT, knowledge management, HRM capability and organization culture based on the pilot study results.

5.3 Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using SPSS software to assess the reliability and internal consistency of the measurement instruments. Cronbach's Alpha was used to evaluate the reliability of each construct, ensuring that the items consistently measured the intended variables. Corrected item-total correlations were also examined to determine the contribution of each item. These analyses provided a basis for confirming that the scales are reliable and the components of information technology, knowledge management, human resource management, and organizational culture were appropriately defined. This process ensured the constructs were suitable for further analysis of their effects on employee performance (Hazzi and Maldaon, 2015).

6.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A pilot study is a crucial preliminary step in preparing for a full-scale investigation, providing researchers with a roadmap for the main study (Patel et al., 2017). Conducting

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a pilot study requires careful attention to key methodological considerations, including back-translation, handling missing data, testing for normality, and assessing reliability, all of which must be addressed before proceeding with actual data collection (Hazzi and Maldaon, 2015). The primary purpose of the pilot study in this research is to confirm the items and components of the measurement instruments. By testing these items, researchers can ensure that each component of information technology, knowledge management, human resource management, and organizational culture is clearly defined, reliable, and appropriately represented. This process also allows for refinement of the survey and incorporation of feedback from pilot testing, ensuring the accuracy and effectiveness of the final study design (Junyong, 2017). Confirming the components at this stage is essential before

performing advanced statistical analyses, such as regression analysis, in the main study (Kayumbi and Wanyoike, 2021).

6.1 Reliability and Validity

Reliability refers to the consistency and stability of a measurement instrument in capturing the intended construct. In this study, reliability was assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha, which measures the internal consistency of the items within each construct (Hussin et al., 2013). According to Pallant (2011) a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.70 or higher is considered acceptable, indicating that the construct reliably measures the underlying concept. Therefore, Cronbach’s alpha was employed in this research to test the reliability of the constructs under study.

Table 1: Reliability statistics for the research instrument

Variables	No item	Cronbach’s Alpha
Employees performance	10	0.854
IT knowledge	5	0.943
IT operations	5	0.947
IT Infrastructure	5	0.919
Information Technology capability	15	0.972
Knowledge Acquisition	7	0.826
Knowledge Conversion	7	0.761
Knowledge Application	7	0.786
Knowledge Management capability	21	0.841
Compensation and Rewards	6	0.853
Job security	6	0.793
Training and Development	7	0.766
Human Resource Management capability	19	0.818
Clan Culture	5	0.719
Adhocracy Culture	5	0.943
Market Culture	5	0.779
Hierarchy Culture	5	0.854
Organizational culture	20	0.878

Table 1 shows that the reliability coefficients for all scales exceeded the acceptable threshold of 0.70, indicating excellent internal consistency (Memon et al., 2017). Specifically, the overall reliability for employee performance was 0.854. Among the independent variables, information technology capability demonstrated the highest reliability at 0.972, followed by knowledge management capability at 0.841, human resource management capability at 0.818, and organizational culture at 0.878. Importantly, the reliability coefficients for all individual components of the constructs also exceeded 0.70, confirming that each dimension is measured consistently and is suitable for further analysis.

6.2 Correlations results

Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the strength and direction of the relationships between the study variables (Okwemba and Njuguna, 2021). This analysis provides insight into how each component of the independent variables is associated with employee performance, helping to identify potential patterns and relationships before conducting further statistical tests (Rehman et al., 2022). The results indicated a significant and positive correlation between all three components of IT capability (IT knowledge, IT operations, and IT infrastructure) and employee performance as shown in Table 2.

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Table 2: Correlation Coefficients Between IT Capability Components and Employee Performance

		IT knowledge	IT operations	IT Infrastructure	Employee Performance
IT knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.866**	.864**	-.114
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.471
IT operations	Pearson Correlation	.866**	1	.920**	-.154
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.331
IT Infrastructure	Pearson Correlation	.864**	.920**	1	-.151
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.339
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.114	-.154	-.151	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.471	.331	.339	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results indicated a significant and positive correlation between all three components of IT capability, IT knowledge, IT operations, and IT infrastructure and employee performance. This suggests that higher levels of IT capability are associated with improved employee performance outcomes. These findings underscore the importance of maintaining robust IT systems, skilled personnel, and effective operational processes to enhance workforce productivity and overall organizational effectiveness. This result aligns with the findings of Darwis et al. (2023) who reported a significant positive influence of information technology on employee performance.

In addition, as shown in Table 3, the results indicated a significant and positive correlation between all three

components of Knowledge Management capability (knowledge acquisition, knowledge conversion, and knowledge application) and employee performance. This suggests that stronger KM practices within the organization are associated with higher levels of employee performance. These findings are consistent with Biswakarma (2018), who examined the impact of selected KM practices on employee job performance among 145 employees of commercial banks in Nepal. The study found that practices such as knowledge creation and acquisition, knowledge filtering, knowledge exchange, and knowledge development positively and significantly contributed to achieving long-term sustainable competitive advantage in the banking sector, thereby enhancing employee performance.

Table 3: Correlation Coefficients Between Knowledge Management Capability Components and Employee Performance

		Employee Performance	Knowledge Acquisition	Knowledge Conversion	Knowledge Application
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	-.159	.176	.100
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.313	.265	.530
Knowledge Acquisition	Pearson Correlation	-.159	1	.692**	-.005
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.313		.000	.976
	N	42	42	42	42
Knowledge Conversion	Pearson Correlation	.176	.692**	1	-.091
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.265	.000		.567
Knowledge Application	Pearson Correlation	.100	-.005	-.091	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.530	.976	.567	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As shown in Table 4, the analysis revealed a positive relationship between the components of Human Resource Management capability (compensation and rewards, job security, and training and development) and employee performance. However, these correlations were not statistically significant, with r-values ranging from -0.224 to 0.148 ($p > 0.05$). Among the HRM components, a significant positive correlation was observed between compensation and rewards and job security ($r = 0.499$, $p = 0.001$), indicating strong internal consistency among HRM practices. Overall, while HRM components are positively associated with

employee performance, their direct impact appears modest in this sample, suggesting that other factors may mediate or strengthen these relationships. These findings align with Aboramadan et al. (2020) who found that HRM practices positively influence employee job performance, supporting the relevance of effective HRM systems in enhancing workforce outcomes. Similarly Shatha *et al* (2021) reported that HRM practices significantly affect employee performance among construction industry employees in Jordan.

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Table 4: Correlation Coefficients Between Human Resource Management Capability Components and Employee Performance

Correlations		Employee Performance	Compensation and Rewards	Job security	Training and Development
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	-.224	.115	.148
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.154	.469	.350
Compensation and Rewards	Pearson Correlation	-.224	1	.499**	.074
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.154		.001	.641
Job security	Pearson Correlation	.115	.499**	1	.270
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.469	.001		.084
	N	42	42	42	42
Training and Development	Pearson Correlation	.148	.074	.270	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.350	.641	.084	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Furthermore, as shown in Table 5, the analysis revealed significant positive correlations between several dimensions of organizational culture and employee performance. Specifically, market culture ($r = 0.489$, $p = 0.001$) and hierarchy culture ($r = 0.933$, $p < 0.001$) were strongly and positively associated with employee performance. Other dimensions, such as clan culture ($r = 0.023$, $p = 0.884$) and adhocracy culture ($r = -0.052$, $p = 0.742$), showed weak and non-significant correlations with employee performance. Additionally, the correlations among the organizational culture dimensions indicate substantial interrelationships, particularly between clan and adhocracy cultures ($r = 0.916$,

$p < 0.001$), clan and market cultures ($r = 0.754$, $p < 0.001$), and market and hierarchy cultures ($r = 0.490$, $p = 0.001$), reflecting overlapping cultural attributes within the organization. These results suggest that while certain cultural dimensions (market and hierarchy) have a direct positive impact on employee performance, others may play a more indirect role or interact with other factors to influence outcomes. This finding is consistent with Al Dhanhani and Abdullah (2021), who reported that organizational culture significantly influences employee job performance in the UAE.

Table 5: Correlation Coefficients Between Organizational Culture Components and Employee Performance

		Employee Performance	Clan Culture	Adhocracy Culture	Market Culture	Hierarchy Culture
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.023	-.052	.489**	.933**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.884	.742	.001	.000
Clan Culture	Pearson Correlation	.023	1	.916**	.754**	.034
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.884		.000	.000	.829
Adhocracy Culture	Pearson Correlation	-.052	.916**	1	.641**	-.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.742	.000		.000	.836
Market Culture	Pearson Correlation	.489**	.754**	.641**	1	.490**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000		.001
Hierarchy Culture	Pearson Correlation	.933**	.034	-.033	.490**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.829	.836	.001	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

7.0 CONCLUSION

The findings of this study support the conceptual framework, indicating that effective integration of Information technology (IT), Knowledge Management (KM), and Human Resource Management (HRM) capabilities is associated with enhanced employee performance, although the strength of these relationships varies across components. Specifically, all three IT capability components and KM capability

components showed significant positive correlations with employee performance, highlighting the critical role of technological infrastructure and knowledge practices in supporting workforce productivity. HRM components demonstrated positive but mostly non-significant correlations, suggesting that their direct effect on performance may be modest and potentially influenced by other organizational factors. Among organizational culture

dimensions, market and hierarchy cultures exhibited strong positive correlations with employee performance, whereas clan and adhocracy cultures had weak and non-significant effects, emphasizing that certain cultural attributes more directly support performance outcomes. Overall, these results confirm that IT and KM capabilities, supported by appropriate cultural dimensions, play a central role in enhancing employee performance, while HRM practices may require further alignment with organizational context to maximize their effectiveness. Therefore, all confirmed components, including HRM practices, can confidently be adopted for further testing using large sample sizes that PLS-SEM as analysis tool to examine direct and indirect effect of IT, KM, HRM and organizational culture on employee performance.

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